

Research paper

The role of neighborhood morphology in enhancing thermal comfort and resident's satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

The unilateral development of built environments in cities leads to imbalances in climatic conditions and micro-climates, followed by indicators such as thermal comfort. Researchers identified the effect of urban morphology's geometry, shape, orientation, and mass-space combination on climate change. Also, the influential role of urban greenspaces in enhancing thermal comfort has been studied. Some results show that strengthening urban greenspaces, regardless of the orientation and proportions of the surrounding space, in some cases can prevent the proper circulation of airflow and adverse effects on thermal comfort. In this research, 10 models of neighborhoods in Tehran (the capital of Iran) were studied based on numerical calculation methods and CFD simulations. These simulations are performed by ENVI-met software, which is well-known software in this field. This study investigates which pattern and geometry in the composition of these spaces, with a constant fraction of the building, green spots, and water and paths, could better enhance thermal comfort. The results show that patterns with non-linear structure and a mass of porous spaces in which green spots are scattered have the best results in enhancing thermal comfort.

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1. Introduction

The world population is 7.8 billion (2021), with a growth rate of 1/11 percent per year expected to reach 10 billion by 2056. By 2030, the United Nations predicts that 60% of the world's population will be living in cities (UN, 2015). Modern infrastructure and environmental conditions encourage people to move to urbanization. Climate change, the urban heat island effect, and air pollution may cause problems due to rapid improvement and industrialization (Hogrefe et al., 2004; Goharian et al., 2022). These challenges can directly influence on healthiness of dwellers, thermal comfort, and augment air conditioning demand (Rosenfeld et al., 1993; Zare et al., 2022).

Due to human activities and the density of the built environment, the urban area or metropolitan area is significantly warmer than the surrounding environment and urban suburbs.

The urban heat island effect (UHI) is the difference in thermal balance between urban and rural areas. The difference is due to heat and momentum transfer changes between the land

surface and the atmosphere in terms of heat storage, partitioning between sensible and latent heat fluxes (Bowen ratio), frictional drag, and the ratio of natural and anthropogenic emissions. (Dousset and Gourmelon, 2003; Vailshery et al., 2013)

UHI is a phenomenon induced by changes in the built environment's balance and thermal attributes (Oke, 1982). Furthermore, wind speeds, cloud cover, season, city and population size, and time of day influence UHI intensities (Arnfield, 2003; Norouzi et al., 2021).

The impacts of the urban heat island on air temperature and urban surface temperatures result in a reduction in human thermal comfort, increased energy demand for cooling, and deterioration in air quality (Wentz et al., 2016; Nazaroff, 2013; Song and Wang, 2015). Many mitigating techniques exist to diminish UHI, including changing urban morphology (building dimensions and spacing, street widths, orientation, ...), enhancing urban cover (paved, water, vegetated), and managing urban metabolism (water, heat, and pollution due to human activities). (Stewart and Oke, 2009). Increased urban shade by greenery is one of the most effective methods (Galenieks, 2017; Zölch et al. 2016; Yeganeh and Kamalizadeh, 2018). Increased greenery or tree coverage provides a cooling effect. It enhances human thermal comfort, according to numerical models. However, the extent of cooling for given vegetation varies depending on the climate zones

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Table 1
Research background.

Authors	Methodology	Discussion	Variables	Results
AlexandreD. Waffle (2017)	<i>Critical Analysis</i>	Agricultural Opportunities in Urban Heat Islands	Air temperature, Anthropogenic Heat, wind speed, solar radiation	Warmer-climate grape types were shown to be capable of producing in Toronto if cultivated in an area with an SVF of 50% or less.
Giulia Ulpiani (2021)	<i>Critical Analysis</i>	The Interaction Between Urban Pollution Island and Urban Heat Island	Temperature, Urban geometric types, urban forms	Local warming and air quality are worsened by urban winds with low-level inversion and convergence, especially at night. In assessing the reciprocal link between UHI and UPI, the impact of increased turbulence in the urban boundary layer is critical.
H.M.P.I.K. Herath (2018)	<i>Simulation and field assessment</i>	As an(UHI) adaptation method, green infrastructure's effects in a tropical Sri Lankan urban environment are being assessed.	Temperature variations, relative humidity	The simulation model may be adopted because all R2 values reported in this investigation are acceptable. The ENVI-met microclimatic model might be employed in tropical Sri Lankan metropolitan areas.
Je-Woo Hong (2019)	<i>Critical Analysis</i>	The temporal dynamics of the urban heat island in Seoul, Korea, have been linked to socioeconomic improvement during the previous half-century.	Urban heat island (UHI), Heatwave	With future changes in the monsoon environment, the UHI will display distinct temporal dynamics, and heat waves in the urban region will be exacerbated if current fast urbanization continues without a move toward sustainable and equitable development.
Zhaoxin.Dai (2017)	<i>Statically Analysis</i>	Impacts of parks and land use on the urban heat island	LST, NDVI, NDBI, main roads, water bodies, parks	Understanding the interaction between landscape form and land surface temperature (LST) is critical for urban heat island reduction.
K.R. Gunawardena (2017)	<i>Critical Analysis</i>	To reduce the severity of urban heat islands, green and blue spaces should be used.	Evapotranspiration, temperature	Greenspace increases surface roughness, which improves convection efficiency rather than evaporation and hence contributes to cooling at the scale of the urban boundary-layer climate. Even though blue space cooling and transportation can be significant throughout the day, nighttime warming is the most likely time when circumstances are the most unpleasant. However, significant synergistic ecological advantages, such as cooling, may be realized when both green and blue infrastructures are used together.
Quanshan Zhao (2018)	<i>Simulation</i>	The influence of tree placement on outdoor microclimates and human thermal comfort	Air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, mean radiant temperature	Numerical models' flexibility allows them to replicate and compare outdoor microclimates and human thermal comfort under various tree placements and configurations. We advise city dwellers to grow shade trees with no canopy overlap.
Yang Xing (2019)	<i>Simulation</i>	The role of vegetation in air pollution deposition and dispersion in urban parks.	Deposition settling velocities, urban park borders	Pollutants from highways can be dispersed into parks by vegetation, effectively increasing pollutant concentrations. Nonetheless, just as changing the geographical distribution of tenants can vary exposure to air pollutants, the distribution of greeneries in a park can change.
Zhaowu Yu (2020)	<i>Critical Analysis</i>	A thresholdsize viewpoint on the cooling impact of urban blue-green area.	Urban heat island (UHI)	The cooling impact of blue-greenspace in terms of size, shape, connectedness, complexity (composition and configuration), seasonal and diurnal differences, latitude and climatic differences, and so on.

at different geographic locations, density or type of greeneries, and building layout or wind corridor design (Hsieh et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2017). Furthermore, trees help reduce CO₂, lowering greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the surrounding microclimate directly and indirectly.

Shading of trees plays a vital role in thermal comfort, but it is crucial to arrange them so that they do not impede the movement of the wind (Zhao et al., 2018). In another study, greenness's effects on reducing the temperature to achieve thermal comfort have been studied. The simulation results show that greenery in urban spaces with green roofs can reduce the temperature by about 0.4 to 1.1 degrees Celsius (Cortes et al., 2022; Yeganeh Mansour, 2020).

Also, the identification of urban geometry based on H/W and SVF parameters has been investigated in various studies. In a study without considering greenery and changes in H/W, urban geometry and its orientations were investigated. The results show

that the linear texture with east–west streets and blocks with low density and confinement, the weakest condition, enclosed and dense blocks, and the central courtyard had the best thermal comfort conditions (Galal et al., 2020) microclimate both directly and indirectly. Table 1 refers to a collection of previous research.

1.1. Objective and research gap

The coexistence of open and greenspaces with different geometries and forms of the neighborhood needs to be further examined and its effect on strengthening and improving thermal comfort conditions and controlling the Urban heat island effect (UHI). The presence of greenspaces and trees according to the direction and proportions of the street canyon can have a favorable or adverse effect on thermal comfort and control of the Urban heat island effect (UHI) by impeding the optimal

Research Design

Fig. 1. Research Design.

airflow circulation. Therefore, examining its effect in different geometries, forms, and orientations of neighborhoods is essential to identify how this effect.

As a result, this study will analyze the feasibility of lowering UHI by various forms and combinations of greenery, water, and

streets, using a numerical simulation modeling program called ENVI-met developed by Micheal Bruse. (Fig. 1)

This study identified neighborhoods from different parts of Tehran (the capital of Iran) with different geometries. Then, by combining the same percentage of open spaces, green and blue

spots, and the layout of buildings in different patterns, it examines the morphology of the neighborhood and measures them in terms of temperature changes and climatic conditions in the simulated environment. Then, the most stable and appropriate patterns are identified to determine the highest efficiency in enhancing thermal comfort and mitigating the Urban heat island effect.

2. Methodology

2.1. Simulations tool

Energy-Based (EB) models and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models are two types of numerical models with different horizontal resolutions. The first category comprises models for various urban components that solve the surface energy balance on a control volume (e.g., a street canyon) for different urban elements (e.g., road, wall, roof, and eventually green areas).

3D models that connect velocity, temperature, and pollutant fields to a more comprehensive simulation of airflow around obstructions make up the second category. They need a high-resolution representation of urban geometry, precision in boundary conditions for all key variables, and sufficient processing resources, which prevent the simulation of long-time windows.

The CFD ENVI-met v4.4.5 model is used to analyze the microclimatic conditions of neighborhoods in this study.

ENVI-met is a computer program designed for 3D atmospheric modeling to simulate the microclimate in the urban environment. It has been used to simulate air flows outdoors and the effects of local microclimates and heat transfer at the building wall or ground surface (Bruse and Fleer, 1998). ENVI-met is frequently utilized in the scientific community for human biometeorology and thermal comfort investigations (Motevalian and Yeganeh, 2020).

ENVI-met comprises two sub-models that interact: (1) a one-dimensional border model with vertical profiles of meteorological data; a three-dimensional core model including processes in the atmosphere, soil, buildings, and plants. It quantifies environmental factors (such as radiation, airflow, turbulence, and humidity) and indices to recreate the microclimate and human thermal comfort conditions (as PET, PMV, PPD)

Essential software calibration was conducted for 10 distinct areas in Tehran to verify the ENVI-met numerical model's capability. The performance-producing procedures of this program use the eulerian approach for the calculation of mass momentum and budget, whose way of solving the flow is based upon the RANS equations and describing the turbulence effects using their $k-\epsilon$ model (Bruse, 2012; ISO 7730-1994, 1994; Kumar and Kar, 2009). The prognostic Equations for a mass conserving wind field $u_i^{t+\Delta t}$ are split into an auxiliary flow field (u^{aux}) and a pressure field (p):

$$\frac{\partial u_i^{t+\Delta t}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial u_i^{aux}}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{\rho} + \nabla p$$

Then the pressure variable is removed from the prognostic equations and led to a set of three prognostic equations for an auxiliary flow field:

$$\frac{\partial u^{aux}}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial u^{aux}}{\partial x_i} = K_m \left(\frac{\partial^2 u^{aux}}{\partial x_i^2} \right) + f(v - v_g) - S_u$$

$$\frac{\partial v^{aux}}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial v^{aux}}{\partial x_i} = K_m \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^{aux}}{\partial x_i^2} \right) + f(u - u_g) - S_v$$

$$\frac{\partial w^{aux}}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial w^{aux}}{\partial x_i} = K_m \left(\frac{\partial^2 w^{aux}}{\partial x_i^2} \right) + g \frac{\theta_{(z)}}{\theta_{ref(z)}} - S_w$$

2.2. Model configuration and site details

Tehran is Iran's capital with around 14 million inhabitants, divided into 22 municipal districts. We have selected a list of 10 different districts in Tehran, characterized by different urban geometry on a neighborhood scale. Such as Gisha, Vahidiyeh, Yousef-Abad, Farahzad, Jomhuri, Ferdowsi, North-Shahrnan, Shahrak-E-Gharb, Janat-Abad, and Narmak, with a diversity of geographical conditions, from the shape of the buildings to the vegetation and water bodies.

Table 2 shows aerial images of the neighborhood and the models created to simulate it in the ENVI-met. A fieldwork measurement and validation effort are carried out to confirm the base pattern model's geometries and ratios. Neighborhoods are built in a 250 * 250 * 30 m (X,Y,Z) dimension. The dimensions of each cell are 2 * 2 * 2 m. Also, a 4 m width buffer was placed around the simulation model for distance with edges (See Table 2). The process of choosing the conditions include, Selected districts => buildings => vegetation => water bodies.

Four parameters were modeled in permanent percent for each district: buildings (51%), greenspaces (17%), water bodies (2%), roads (24%), and 6% for wasteland. Building boundaries were digitalized (based on a Google map) with a constant height of 18 m. The greenspaces in each district are consistently mixed with trees (40%), shrubs (20%), and grass (20%). (40 percent) (see Fig. 2).

2.3. Meteorological conditions

Tehran has a continental climate with Mediterranean precipitation patterns and a cold semi-arid climate (Köppen climatic classification: BSk). Tehran's climate is mainly determined by its physical position, bordered to the north by the high Alborz mountains and to the south by the country's central desert. Summer is lengthy, hot, and dry, with little rain, but relative humidity is low, making the heat bearable. ENVI-met simulations need a set of meteorological parameters (Bruse, 2012). The simulation was conducted using the numerical micro-climate model ENVI-met hourly climatic data. Air temperature, MRT, wind speed, and relative humidity were simulated for 5 h, from 12:00 to 16:00, for each pattern on June 21, 2020. The information is provided in Table 3.

2.4. Buildings and street layout

The building boundary information is manually digitized at a constant height of 18 m based on Google Maps. Street canyons are separated into two orientations: North-South, and East-West. Also, street canyons are divided into 2 types: parallel and intersection. (Fig. 3)

Finally, we calculated the H/W ratio, in which H defines the building's height, and W indicates the street's width. The buildings' height is 18 m in all scenarios, while the street width varies between 12, 16, and 24 m. (Ratio H/W: 0.75, 1.125, 1.5) (Fig. 4) According to Ali-Toudert et al. (2005), Ali-Toudert and Mayer (2007), Oke (1992) and Santamouris (1992), emissivity and albedo of urban's surfaces are influential on urban heat islands and thermal comfort. Therefore, these values were considered constant in all patterns. (Table 4)

2.5. Greenspaces and water bodies

There were different arrangements of greenspace distribution in the studied sites, such as Surrounding ring, Network, Axial, linear E-W (East-West) and N-S (North-South) orientation, and courtyard. Three green structures (Trees, dense grass, and hedges)

Fig. 2. Case studies map (Tehran, Iran).

Fig. 3. Streets layout.

Fig. 4. Street Canyon Ratios(H/W).

are selected for the Simulation's greenspace (Table 5). For all scenarios, a fixed 15-meter-high Acer platanoides deciduous tree is used. We used 50 cm tall, thick grass and 2 m tall, dense hedges in simulation models to replicate urban lawns (See Table 5).

Because this study aimed to analyze the effects of trees and other plant patterns on outdoor microclimates and urban heat islands, we used the same tree type (Acer platanoides) in all simulated scenarios. Also, Three different sources are used in the model for

Table 2
Sites and Patterns description.

District(Pattern)	1-Gisha	2-Vahidiyeh	3-Yousef-Abad	4-Farahzad
Location				
Model				
Greenspace Dispersion	Low	Medium	High	High
Greenspace	Concentrated- Area	Concentrated- Area	Scattered- Linear	Scattered- Area
Water body	Scattered- Linear	Scattered- Linear	Scattered- Linear	Scattered- Linear

District(Pattern)	5-Jomhuri	6-Ferdowsi	7-North-Shahran	8-Shahrak-E-Gharb
Location				
Model				
Greenspace Dispersion	Low	High	Medium	Medium
Greenspace	Concentrated- Area	Scattered- Area	Scattered- Linear	Scattered- Area
Water body	Concentrated- Area	Scattered- Area	Scattered- Area	Scattered- Linear

District(Pattern)	9-Janat Abad	10- West- golbarg
Location		
Model		
Greenspace Dispersion	Low	Medium
Greenspace	Concentrated- Area	Scattered- Area
Water body	Scattered- Linear	Concentrated- Area

- Greenspaces
- Water bodies
- Streets and roads
- Buildings

Greenspace Dispersion Level:

Represents the amount of composition and mixing of greenspace in the neighborhood context. Includes 3 levels: **High, Medium, Low**

* Greenspace and Water bodies include 2 categories of features :

- **Concentrated** or **Scattered**
- **Area** or **Linear**

(In terms of geometry and dimensions)

blue spaces and water bodies, such as a 4 m depth fountain, line, and area.

3. Results and discussion

After completing the simulations, thermal comfort calculations were performed for all ten neighborhood patterns according

to the PMV standard by Bio-met software. Bio-met is a post-processor tool for calculating Human Thermal Comfort Indices from ENVI-met model output files. The Thermal comfort standard is an index of the thermal sensation known as the predicted mean vote (PMV) index. PMV index is a function of six variables: physiological variables and the rest are environmental variables. PMV index values range from -3 to +3, which describes the feeling of cold to hot (ISO7730,1997). Significant results were

Fig. 5. Thermal comfort distribution based on PMV index in 12:00 and 16:00 patterns.

Fig. 6. Dispersion and concentration of PMV index values in sample points by space quality (1- Roads 2- Open, green and blue spaces).. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 3
Meteorological parameters.

Parameter	Definition	Value
Meteorological Conditions	All the cases	
	Potential air temperature	25
	Relative humidity	Min: 20, Max: 40
	Wind direction	Parallel/Perpendicular to the street direction (E–W)
	Wind speed	2.5 m/s

reviewed by analyzing neighborhood patterns and the changes in the thermal comfort range (Fig. 5). The results indicate that street orientation had the most critical effect in defining thermal comfort range. During the simulation, north–south streets in the PMV index moved from the warm to the cold range. (From 12:00 to 16:00). This behavior is reversed for East–West(E–W) streets. Somehow, it moved from the Cold to Warm range of PMV during simulations. It should be noted that the changes in the width of streets have not shown any different results in mentioned behavior. Mentioned fluctuations (in PMV values) are more seen in grid patterns than in the other patterns. The concentration of the greenspaces in a specific area separated from the residential textures and buildings was ineffective regarding thermal comfort and temperature balance. (Pattern 1, 2, 5)

The residential’s greenspaces and water bodies on the East–West axis have created open areas. These open areas, along with greenery and water, have been able to play an influential role in controlling thermal comfort at different hours By Wind flow circulation. Somehow, it has placed most of the areas in the range of PMV=0 index in the first hour of simulation and the relatively warm range in the last hours of the day. (Pattern 3, 4)

However, the presence of green space in the north–south axis has led the PMV index to the cold range (especially in the last hours). (Pattern 10)

Courtyard patterns that create individual parcels have an influential role in thermal comfort. However, significant shading has changed the index values and placed it in the cold range in the last hour of the simulation. (Pattern 8). Also, unlike the greenery, water bodies in this pattern alone had no tangible effect on improving thermal comfort. (Pattern 7)

Removing greenery from the neighborhood’s texture and placing it in a peripheral green belt was ineffective in improving the neighborhood’s thermal comfort. (Patterns 9 and 7). The result was the same for the mass of green space concentrated within the texture. (pattern5)

It should be noted that the presence of large water bodies such as pattern 9 has a temperature–controlling effect only in the surrounding area. In the early hours of simulation, it is cooler than the adjacent area, and in the late hours, it is warmer.

The mentioned items were also acknowledged in irregular and organic patterns. In a way, the east–west axis open spaces with greenery were in a suitable range regarding thermal comfort. (pattern6)

After simulating all neighborhood patterns, the obtained data were analyzed based on the quality of points and different neighborhood patterns to understand the fluctuations and changes in thermal comfort. Sample Points 5, 6, 9, 10 are grouped as greenery, water bodies, and open spaces in group1. Sample Points 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8 are grouped as streets and intersections in group 2. (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6 shows that the density of sample points in group 2 ranges from 0.5 to 1 in the thermal comfort index. The range around 0.5 (PMV index) for group 1 refers to the cooling effect of about 0.5 degrees of greenery and water bodies compared to asphalt streets. Also, the fluctuations of changes in group 1 are more controlled than in group 2. An increase in humidity due to trees, greenery, and water areas and the thermal capacity of water as a temperature control feature on fluctuation ranges reduced the scatter of points in group 1. (Fig. 6)

Next, we examined the neighborhoods separately; 10 sample points were extracted from each 10 simulation models and analyzed to examine their fluctuations within 4 h of the simulation. Fig. 7 shows this category for 10 patterns per hour.

From Fig. 7, it can be concluded that concentrating greenspace in one part of the neighborhood and removing scattered will make the neighborhood warmer. Reducing the surrounded and concentrated green masses and distributing increases the connection with the arteries and wind flow, thus improving thermal comfort conditions. (Pattern 2) Also, Thermal comfort is controlled better in the patterns in which the greenery is scattered in the neighborhood. However, the orientation of the streets and wind direction should be considered. Ignoring these two essential issues(Street orientation and wind direction) will thermal comfort (Pattern 10)

Therefore, patterns 8, 9, 3, and even 2 have concentrated the PMV index values in the warm range (0.5 to 1) in all hours. So, fewer fluctuations and scattering can be seen in their values.

Fig. 8 shows the dispersion of the thermal comfort index of 1–10 sample points in all patterns(Number of patterns based on Table 2), which confirms the presented results In another way.

Table 4
Characteristics of Urban surfaces in Simulation model.

Name	Albedo	Emissivity	Roughness length					
Soil	0.20	0.95	0.015					
Asphalt Road	0.15	0.95	0.010					
Wall and roof Profile (mat1:inside–mat 3:Outside)								
Wall Material Name (Based on ENVI-met database)	Thickness (m)	Absorption	Transmission	Reflection	Emissivity	Specific Heat (J/Kg*k)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m*K)	Density (Kg/m ³)
1- Default Plaster	0.01	0.5	0	0.5	0.9	850	0.6	1500
2- Default Insulation	0.12	0.5	0	0.5	0.9	1500	0.07	400
3- Default Concrete	0.18	0.5	0	0.5	0.9	850	1.6	2220

Table 5
Characteristics of greenery.

Name	Classification	Height	Diameter/Width	FSA (Foliage Shortwave Albedo)	FST (Foliage Shortwave Transmittance)
Grass	Deciduous	0.50 m	1 m	0.15	0.20
Hedge	Deciduous	2 m	1 m	0.20	0.25
Tree	Deciduous (Acer Platanoides)	15 m	7 m	0.18	0.30

Fig. 7. Dispersion and concentration of PMV index values in sample points by patterns and test hours.

Also, similar to Fig. 8, the scatter of PPD index values for all 10 sample points out of 10 patterns in the simulation hours is shown as a heatmap, which can help better understand and confirm the results. The PPD, or index that creates a quantitative forecast of the percentage of thermally unsatisfied inhabitants (i.e., too warm or too cold), may be established once the PMV has been calculated. The percentage of persons expected to feel local pain is calculated using PPD. (ISO7730,1997) (see Fig. 9).

4. Conclusion

Increasing the uneven development of cities and built environments in cities leads to disruption of residents' temperature balance and thermal comfort. The geometry and morphology of urban neighborhoods, the orientation and distribution of greenspaces, mass and space can improve thermal comfort conditions in the micro-climates of neighborhoods. In this study, by identifying 10 patterns of neighborhoods in Tehran and using

Fig. 8. PMV index in patterns' sample points during simulation hours.

Fig. 9. PPD index in patterns' sample points during simulation hours.

CFD simulation by ENVI-met, the quality of changes in climate conditions and thermal comfort in a constant amount and fraction of green surfaces of water spots, paths and buildings were measured.

The results show that changes in the geometry and morphology of the neighborhood in a constant ratio of greenspaces, water bodies, and buildings can affect the neighborhood's climate and subsequently affect their thermal comfort and satisfaction. These features can improve the thermal comfort index by up to 0.5 degrees. Also, the amplitude of thermal comfort fluctuations decreased by about 0.3 degrees in the PMV index. Organic patterns with suitable mass-space integration had a better role in improving thermal comfort. These patterns limit a larger area of a neighborhood within the neutral range of the PMV index during the day. It should be noted that the presented results do not mean the removal of concentrated green areas. Large-scale green areas such as local parks and green spots have other roles, such as strengthening residents' social, cultural, and psychological aspects and effectively strengthening the neighborhood's ecosystem, ecosystem services, and biodiversity. Paying attention to strengthening residents' private greenspaces such as yards, private gardens, and even roofs and green walls in homes will be effective. The study of green spots in the seasonal model to propose suitable and sustainable species and the percentage of use of different types of plants can be one of the items that can be monitored in future research.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sahar Ahmadi: Paper draft, Simulation, Data collection, Literature review. **Mansour Yeganeh:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Final editing. **Mohammadreza Baradaran Motie:** Data visualization, Data analysis, Paper draft. **Azin Gilandoust:** Data collection.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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